

Joint meeting

The Fifth International Symposium on Neurocardiology
NEUROCARD 2013

The Fourth International Symposium on
Noninvasive Electrocardiology

October 17th – 18th, 2013
Hotel Metropol Palace, Belgrade, Serbia

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAMME
&
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Editors:

Professor dr Branislav Milovanovic
Associate Professor dr Cristian Podoleanu

University Press Târgu Mureș
2013

October 17th – 18th, 2013
Hotel Metropol Palace, Belgrade, Serbia

Joint meeting

The Fifth International Symposium on Neurocardiology
NEUROCARD 2013

The Fourth International Symposium on
Noninvasive Electrocardiology

**SCIENTIFIC PROGRAMME
&
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS**

Editors:

Professor Dr Branislav Milovanovic
Associate Professor Dr Christin Podoleanu

NEUROCARD

ISSN 2069 – 0169
ISSN-L 2069 – 0169

is published by
University Press Târgu Mureș

October 17th – 18th, 2013
Hotel Metropol Palace, Belgrade, Serbia

VENTRICLE SEGMENTATION IN NEAR-BASE AND NEAR-APEX SLICES OF MR IMAGES

Djordje Starčević¹

Šveljo Olivera², Spirovski Milena², Lončar-Turukalo Tatjana¹, Petrović Vladimir¹
¹FTN-University of Novi Sad, ²Diagnostic Imaging Centre, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina,
 Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Background: Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is considered a reference modality for non-invasive assessment of cardiac morphology and function. Important information on the heart's contractility can be obtained from the MRI images using the short-axis view. MRI image processing implies segmentation of cardiac ventricles as a prerequisite for evaluation of ventricular function. Variability among subjects, structural irregularities and piecewise appearance of the ventricles in near-base and near-apex slices of the short-axis view present a special difficulty in segmentation process. We show how a computer vision approach can be used to automatically segment all fragments of the ventricles.

Objectives: This paper presents an automatic method for segmentation of relevant ventricular structures. Region of interest (ROI) containing the heart is defined. Segmentation is performed using the multiscale image representation called the Inter-Coefficient Product (ICP).

Methods: MRI images used were acquired at the Diagnostic Imaging Centre, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia. Automatic segmentation initialises by locating ROI using morphological activity detection between consecutive cardiac cycle frames. Segmentation is performed using ICP. The ICP is a decimated pyramid of complex values based on the Dual-Tree Complex Wavelet Transform. The complex phases of its coefficients correspond to the angles of dominant directional features in their support regions.

Results and conclusion: Proposed automatic ROI definition algorithm successfully locates the heart region. Subsequent automatic segmentation algorithm was able to detect all ventricular fragments. The proposed automatic segmentation approach is therefore an efficient method for extracting relevant ventricle structures. Resulting images show variation in size, shape and number of these fragments. Focus of future work should be automatic classification of these sections and developing suitable models.

[1] R. Anderson et al., "Determining Multiscale Image Feature Angles from Complex Wavelet Phases", *ICIAR '05 Proceedings of the Second international conference on Image Analysis and Recognition*, pp. 490 – 498, 2005.